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The Impact of Emotional Intelligence on Academic Achievements of Students at University of Mianwali

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Abstract

The main goal of the current study was to examine “The impact of emotional intelligence on academic achievements of students at university level”. The nature of the current study was quantitative and correlational research design was applied. University of Mianwali was selected as population of the study and undergraduate students of university of Mianwali, was selected as targeted population. The sample will include from four departments (Department of Urdu, Department of English) from faculty of arts and humanities and (Department of Psychology and Department of Education) from faculty of social sciences. The sample was selected through simple random sampling. The sample included 400 students from the above-mentioned departments' regular and self-support programs; B.S (2nd, 6th and 8th semester). An adopted questionnaire of Wong and law Emotional Intelligence Scale WLIES developed by Wong & Law (2002) was used. Academic achievements was measured through students CGPA. Data was collected by using both means online through Google forms. Data were analyzed through inferential statistics (correlation and t test) with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Pearson correlation coefficient showed an insignificant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievements of the respondents. The difference between male and female emotional intelligence was insignificant. The difference between male and female emotional intelligence was also insignificant. It was recommended on the basis of the results that universities need to conduct seminar and workshop to spread awareness about emotional intelligence so that the mental issues of the students addressed and their academic achievement enhanced.

Key words: Emotional Intelligence, Academic Achievement, Students, Mianwali, University

Introduction

The ability of mind and conventional scales of intelligence are not sole elements that have influence on the progress of students at higher level education. It has been demonstrated that academic achievement could be predicted by regulation of self and mental intelligence but intelligence of emotion has become prominent factor significantly. The skill in someone to diagnose, grasp, and control own emotions as well as those of others in everyday life is acknowledged as emotional intelligence (Antonopoulou, 2024). Emotional intelligence has significant impact on learning of behavior, interpersonal association, management of stress and adaptability. But in contradiction, cognitive intelligence is only related to the process of mind (Liu et al., 2021; Zafar & Akhtar, 2023). Emotional intelligence is crucial for balancing the social skills, ability to cope stress as well as personal responsibility; emotional intelligence also enhances the stability of emotions, effective communication and resilient behavior. An indispensable but little-studied topic, expressly at level of higher education, there is the connection between students' academic lives and emotional intelligence. Apart from this the rising interest of emotional intelligence related to field of health, education and business but still there is need of researches at university level regarding students' performance because most of the literature is students of secondary schools of professional settings.

The first model was presented by Salovey and Mayer (1990) and most famous model was of the Goleman (1995), after that this idea has been extensively researched (Singh et al., 2022; Akram et al., 2024). According to Busu (2020) and Arshad et al. (2024), emotional intelligence is referred as the capacity to accurately recognize emotions, apply emotional knowledge in day-to-day tasks, and control emotions in a variety of contexts, both individually and in collaboration. Emotional intelligence (EI) is now recognized in academic institutions as one of the key components that, in addition to cognitive intelligence, help students succeed.

Academic achievement is collection of complex elements including social, emotional, physical and psychological, as opposed to the narrow measurement of intelligent quotient (Preeti, 2003). Overall, intelligent quotient and emotional intelligence both influence the pupils academic achievement. In educational context, the history of emotional intelligence is very long. Teachers started to introduce various related construct in the late 1970's i.e., personal intelligence, "social development," and "emotional learning" into their curricula even before the phrase become popular widely. These beginning sought to improve the emotional intelligence and social skills of the kids. Later on the phenomenon of emotional intelligence have gained the recognition after the revolutionary work of Goleman's (1995), which shift focus towards professional and personal success.

There are different element improved leadership, teamwork, flexibility, and stress management in students associated with emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence and academic achievement are related to each other. Particularly, the life of college aspirant focus on self-regulated learning and capacity to manage stress by own (Rode et al., 2007). The pupils with high emotional intelligence are more motivated, less stressed and optimist in challenging situation; and all of these have good influence on the academic achievement. Many researches evidenced the benefits of the EI in the classrooms. For instance, according to Joibari and Mohammadtaheri (2011), that scholars with training of emotional intelligence and social skills perform good

academically than their classmates. Similarly, Sanchez-Ruiz et al. (2013) and Qaiser et al. (2019) depicted a strong positive association in academic achievement and emotional intelligence. According to Perera & DiGiacomo (2015), the coping strategies could be promoted, adjustment in school setting become easy and builds resilience (Ononye et al., 2022). EI improves academic engagement, according to other research (Dehyadegary et al., 2012; Maguire et al., 2017). All of these results demonstrate how important emotional intelligence (EI) is for fostering students' academic and personal development.

In number of ways emotional intelligence is defined. Some academics defined it as sum of non-cognitive skills that include socially and emotionally intelligent actions (Goleman, 2001). And other academics defined it as reflection of self-perceived capacity to analyze, understand and use of knowledge to be connected with emotions (Petrides & Furnham, 2001). Mayer et al. (2008), defined emotional quotient as a subset of social intelligence that focuses on identifying and controlling one's own emotions as well as those of others in order to influence behavior and thought. The ability model and the trait model are the two prominent models that emerged as a result of these divergent viewpoints. The ability model deals with cognitive skills that can be examined objectively and include perception of emotional information, interpretation and application (Allen et al., 2010; Petrides & Furnham, 2001). However, in contrast trait model put more focus on self-reported behavior inclinations and emotional capacity (Bar-On, 2006; Cooper & Petrides, 2010).

The use of emotional intelligence is increased in leadership and organization context outside of academia. Many companies include emotional intelligence training for their staff development programs success in career and balanced mental and physical health (Goleman, 1995). The emerging theories of social and emotional intelligence are imperative for good leadership because they promote complexity, flexibility, and adaptation (Boal & Whitehead, 1992).

Nevertheless, still gaps exists in the literature about valid emotional intelligence metric that how they are linked with professional and educational settings. In summary, EI is crucial part of students growth that goes beyond conventional ideas of intelligence. This research gap will be filled by the current study as it examined its effect on university students' academic performance. By providing both theoretical insights and real-world implications for improving academic achievements, the findings will help create a more comprehensive understanding of educational success. Through this research, emotional intelligence (EI) can be acknowledged as a significant predictor of student accomplishment as well as a basis for more comprehensive educational reform that aims to foster students' emotional and personal development in addition to their cognitive growth. The current study seeks to examine the influence of EI on the academic performance of university students, thereby contributing to both theory and practice. Despite significant theoretical work on the topic, there is limited empirical evidence on how different dimensions of EI affect achievement in higher education. Findings from this research can provide valuable insights for teachers, administrators, and policymakers in designing educational programs that integrate emotional intelligence training, thereby creating more supportive learning environments.

Literature Review

Emotional intelligence is the skills to keep an eye on own and others emotions and to differentiate between them (Mayer and Salovey, 1990). According to the above definition, it has some basic elements including self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. Emotionally intelligent people are good in making judgments, communicating with others effectively and understanding effects of emotions; these are crucial for educational and professional settings for leadership, team work and dealing with conflicts. These two terms emotions and intelligence were analyzed separately in the early 1900. At that time emotions were looked psychological and physiological response and psychometric traditions based on the assessment of IQ in research. But later on with the perspective of Darwin's evolutionary perspective, emotions was considered culturally molded as strong emphasis was put on its adaptive role. After this, according to the multiple intelligence theory of Gardner's (1983), interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligence were added with focus on social and emotional abilities.

Study of neuroscience defined emotion as affective and cognition as cognitive brain circuits. The idea of EI started getting popular day by day and Goleman's book and Time magazine's in 1995 argued that emotional intelligence was more important for success than IQ. Multiple theories and instruments were used and this phenomenon spread in corporate behavior, psychology, and education since the late 1990s (Mayer et al., 2008). The approach of Bar-On (2003) about emotional intelligence covers various skills to handle stress, management and flexibility. Since university students mainly deal with academic stress, social adaptability, and professional preparation. High EI students are better at handling stress, adjusting to new situations, and forming closer bonds with others (MacCann et al., 2020). Students that possess emotional intelligence exhibit improved coping mechanisms, increased drive, and increased perseverance in their studies (Merkowitz & Earnest, 2006; Snyder & Lopez, 2002). According to research, emotional intelligence (EI) has a good impact on academic performance, social adjustment, and mental health (Mohzan et al., 2013). Students that are emotionally literate are able to change bad feelings into positive ones, which promotes academic performance and resilience (Vandervoort, 2006). Therefore, universities need to incorporate emotional and social development into their curricula in addition to developing cognitive skills (Cohen, 1999; Topping et al., 2000).

Emotional intelligence and academic success are influenced by several factors. Students who have developed emotional literacy are better able to manage stress, anger, and fear in healthy ways. Learning results can be improved and healthier interpersonal relationships can be fostered by programs that emphasize empathy, cooperation, and social ideals. Academic success is influenced by EQ and drive in addition to IQ. Perseverance and flexibility are higher among students with higher EI and motivation (Rode et al., 2007). Teachers and parental guidance are essential in creating emotionally supportive learning environments and setting an example of emotional control. Because of the uncertainty of academic assignments and the self-directed character of higher education, Rode et al. (2007) contended that emotional intelligence (EI) predicts academic performance. Strong self-control helps students handle stress and workloads more effectively. Academic results and EI are linked in an increasing amount of study. Due to the

fact that pupils with high EI are more capable of self-directed learning and problem-solving, Rode et al. (2007) discovered a positive correlation between EI and academic achievement.

This study uses the four-branch ability model developed by Mayer et al. (2004), which focuses on understanding emotion, controlling emotion, sensing emotion, and using emotion to aid in reasoning. These skills demonstrate how emotional processing is incorporated into goal-achieving, problem-solving, and decision-making. The framework offers an organized method for investigating the ways in which emotional intelligence (EI) affects university students' academic performance.

Following hypothesis were made on the basis of above literature:

There is significant correlation between the respondents' academic achievement and emotional intelligence.

There is significant gender difference between the respondents' academic achievement and emotional intelligence.

Methodology

This study used a correlational research approach and was quantitative in nature. The current study's population consisted of all University of Mianwali students. The faculty of arts and humanities and the faculty of social sciences were the sources of the sample. Four departments Urdu, English, psychology, and education were also chosen from the selected faculties. To guarantee variety, 400 male and female students made up this sample using random sampling was employed. An adopted measure, the Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLIES) (Wong & Law, 2002), was employed in this study. Along with the instruments, demographic information was also gathered, including Name, Class, Subject, Department, and CGPA. The dependent variable was academic performance, whereas the independent variable was emotional intelligence. The students' CGPA was used to gauge their academic performance. The instrument's high level of reliability was demonstrated by the computed Cronbach's alpha value of .77. Both physical and online methods were used to collect the data for this study. Online data collection was done using a Google form. The researcher collected data by visiting departments in person. Every ethical guideline was adhered to in this investigation. The participants were fully informed of the research's goal. Their personal data was kept confidential. Participants were not pressured into participating in this study; participation was entirely voluntary. The information gathered was put to use for scholarly studies. t-test analysis, and Pearson correlation was employed.

Correlation Analysis

Table 1 Correlation analysis between emotional intelligence and academic achievement of students

		Academic Achievement
Emotional Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	.073
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.143

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 shows how respondents' academic performance and emotional intelligence related to one another. The respondents' academic performance and emotional intelligence are

related, according to the Pearson correlation coefficient, which is statistically insignificant ($r = .073$ $P = .143$). According to the respondents' academic achievement and emotional intelligence, the alternative hypothesis was disproved.

t test analysis

Table 2 *Difference between Emotional Intelligence of Male and Female Student's*

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	S.D	S.E Mean	t	p-value
EI	Male	141	61.2057	8.67057	.73019	1.369	.751
	Female	259	59.9884	8.40057	.52199	1.356	

The investigator used a t-test (0.05 as a significance level).

Because the estimated p-value is more than the significance level, i.e., $.751 < 0.05$, the alternative hypothesis is rejected. Table 2's $p = .751$ value explained that there is an insignificant difference between the emotional intelligence of male and female students.

Table 3

Difference between Academic Achievement of Male and Female Student's

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	S. D	S.E Mean	t	p-value
CGPA (Optional)	Male	141		.35764	.03012	.309	.954
	Female	259	3.2784	.36393	.02261	.310	

The investigator used a t-test (0.05 as a significance level).

Since the computed p-value is greater than the significance level, or $.954 < 0.05$, the alternative hypothesis is rejected. Table 3's $p = .954$ value clarified that there is an insignificant difference between the CGPAs of male and female students.

Discussions of the Study:

Emotional intelligence's influence on university-level students' academic performance was the primary goal of the current study. Based on the results of this study, there is no statistically significant correlation between students' academic performance and their emotional intelligence (EI). Emotional intelligence has a major influence in the relationship between academic achievement and deviant conduct, according to Petrides et al. (2004). The findings of this study did not support the findings of current research. Some research findings indicate that there is no substantial correlation between academic achievement and output and emotional intelligence, whereas other findings contradict each other and support a considerable association (Alexender, 2018). In contrast to the current study, another study reported a positive significant link between academic achievement/output and emotional intelligence (Turi et al., 2020; Rehman, 2017). According to Rehman (2017), academic success is influenced by emotional intelligence. According to other studies, adolescents with emotional intelligence are more likely to succeed academically (Fernandez et al. 2012). The impact of emotional intelligence on academic achievement and performance is substantial. Emotionally intelligent students are more likely to be motivated to accomplish their goals (Yelkikalan et al., 2012). Pupils that possess strong emotional intelligence

are more successful in school and are better able to control and inspire themselves (Parker et al. 2004). Students place great importance on their academic achievement/output, which is demonstrated by their grades or CGPA.

Male and female students' emotional intelligence differences were found to be statistically negligible in the current investigation. Male and female managers' emotional intelligence ratings did not differ significantly, according to Mandell & Pherwani's (2003) study, which suggests gender may not be a determining factor in EI. The authors of a meta-analysis on emotional intelligence and demographic factors found that there were very little to no gender variations in emotional intelligence amongst studies (Van et al., 2005).

Based on current study, there was no statistically significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female. According to a survey of middle school pupils, self-discipline was a greater predictor of academic achievement than gender (Duckworth & Seligman, 2006). They also discovered that grade inequalities between genders were statistically insignificant when accounting for motivation. This meta-analysis showed that, especially in higher education settings, women perform slightly better than males overall in terms of grades, but the difference is small and usually not statistically significant (Voyer & Voyer, 2016).

Conclusions of the Study:

The primary objective of the present study was to examine "the influence of emotional intelligence on university-level students' academic performance." A statistically insignificant correlation between students' academic achievement and emotional intelligence (EI) was found in the current study's findings. Male and female students' emotional intelligence differences were found to be statistically negligible in the current investigation. The current study found that the academic achievement gap between male and female pupils was statistically negligible.

Recommendation of the Study:

1. This study only included two faculty members from the University of Mianwali in Mianwali. It's possible that the study's findings don't apply to the University of Mianwali as a whole. By incorporating more faculty from the University of Mianwali, Mianwali, the study might be broadened.
2. Finding the "Effect Emotional Intelligence on the Academic Achievement of Higher Education Students" was the study's primary goal. However, in more research, we can observe how the teacher-class interaction moderates the impact of self-efficacy or other factors on academic performance.
3. It will be more beneficial if we incorporate qualitative assessments into further research. By using qualitative analysis, researchers can closely examine or document respondents' answers.

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